

Agro2Circular

D9.4 – Data Management Plan (final)

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List of abbreviations

- **A2C:** Agro2Circular
- **APC:** Article Processing Charge
- **DIS:** Data Integration System
- **DMP:** Data Management Plan
- **DOI:** Digital Object Identifier
- **DPO:** Data Protection Officer
- **DSA:** Data Sharing Agreement
- **EC:** European Commission
- **EG:** Ethylene Glycol
- **FAIR:** Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
- **FNC:** File Naming Convention
- **F&V:** Fruits & Vegetables
- **GA:** General Assembly
- **GDPR:** General Data Protection Regulation
- **LCA:** Life Cycle Assessment
- **PHBV:** Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate)
- **PE/PET:** Polyethylene/Polyethylene Terephthalate
- **PLA:** Polylactic Acid
- **PID:** Persistent Identifier
- **RA:** Research Action
- **TPA:** Terephthalic Acid
- **WP:** Work Package

Glossary

- **Access authorization** - A control mechanism that restricts data access to specific users based on authentication criteria and established permissions.
- **Accessibility of data** - A FAIR principle stating that data should be available and accessible to authorised users with clear access conditions and authentication mechanisms where necessary.
- **Anonymisation** - The process of removing or modifying personal information in data to prevent the direct or indirect identification of individuals.
- **Archiving of data** - The process of storing and preserving data in structured and accessible formats for long-term availability.
- **Article Processing Charges (APCs)** - Fees paid to publishers to make scientific publications freely accessible under open access policies.
- **Biodegradability** - The ability of a material to decompose in the environment through microbial activity without generating harmful waste.
- **Circular economy** - An economic model focused on minimising waste and maximising resource efficiency through reuse, recycling, and sustainable production processes.
- **Confidentiality of data** - A principle ensuring that sensitive or private information is protected from unauthorised access and only available to approved users.
- **Controlled access data** - Data that are subject to restrictions due to confidentiality, intellectual property rights, or ethical considerations, requiring approval for access.
- **Data availability** - The principle ensuring that data are accessible for use at the required time and in the appropriate format.
- **Data cleaning** - The process of identifying and correcting errors, inconsistencies, or duplicates in a dataset to improve data quality.
- **Data compatibility** - The ability of different datasets to be integrated and used together without conflicts in format, structure, or meaning.
- **Data confidentiality** - A data protection measure ensuring that information remains private and accessible only to authorised users.

- **Data curation** - The process of managing and maintaining data to ensure their long-term usability, accessibility, and quality.
- **Data embargo** - A period during which data are not publicly available, typically to allow for scientific publication or to protect intellectual property rights.
- **Data ethics** - The principles and practices governing the responsible collection, use, and sharing of data, ensuring compliance with legal and moral standards.
- **Data findability** - A FAIR principle ensuring that data are structured and indexed in a way that makes them easily discoverable by users and machines.
- **Data governance** - The policies, standards, and procedures that ensure data are managed effectively, securely, and in compliance with legal and ethical regulations.
- **Data integrity** - The accuracy, consistency, and reliability of data throughout their lifecycle, ensuring that information remains unaltered and valid.
- **Data interoperability** - The ability of different systems, formats, and tools to exchange, process, and use data without losing meaning or integrity.
- **Data lifecycle** - The series of stages that data go through, from creation and collection to processing, storage, sharing, and long-term preservation.
- **Data management** - The set of processes for collecting, storing, processing, distributing, and preserving data throughout a project's lifecycle.
- **Data Management Plan (DMP)** - A document outlining how research data will be handled during and after a project's completion, ensuring accessibility, security, and preservation.
- **Data mining** - The process of analysing large datasets to discover patterns, correlations, and insights through computational methods.
- **Data protection** - The policies and measures implemented to ensure the security, privacy, and legal compliance of data processing activities, in line with regulations such as the **GDPR**.
- **Data quality control** - The procedures used to ensure that data are accurate, reliable, and fit for purpose before being used for research or decision-making.
- **Data reusability** - A FAIR principle ensuring that data are documented and structured so they can be effectively used in future research or applications.
- **Data repository** - A digital platform where datasets are stored, managed, and shared, such as **Zenodo**, **Mendeley Data**, or **CrossRef**.

- **Data scalability** - The ability of a dataset to accommodate growth in size or complexity while remaining accessible and usable.
- **Data security** - A set of measures and protocols designed to protect data from unauthorised access, breaches, or loss.
- **Data sharing agreement (DSA)** - A formal contract defining how data will be exchanged, used, and protected between organisations or researchers.
- **Data sovereignty** - The concept that data are subject to the laws and governance of the country in which they are stored or processed.
- **Data standardization** - The process of converting data into common formats and structures to ensure interoperability and compatibility across different systems.
- **Data stewardship** - The responsibility of managing, protecting, and ensuring the ethical use of data throughout their lifecycle.
- **Data sustainability** - A strategy to ensure that data remain accessible, useful, and properly stored for long-term use.
- **Data traceability** - The ability to track the origin, modifications, and access to a dataset, ensuring transparency and accountability.
- **Depolymerisation** - A chemical or enzymatic process that breaks down polymers into their original monomers for reuse, commonly applied in plastic recycling.
- **Digital object identifier (DOI)** - A unique and permanent identifier assigned to digital resources, such as datasets and research publications, to ensure long-term accessibility.
- **Encryption** - A security measure that protects data by converting them into a coded format that can only be accessed with a decryption key.
- **Ethical data governance** - The application of ethical principles to data management, ensuring responsible handling, fairness, and compliance with legal frameworks.
- **FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)** - A set of guidelines ensuring that research data are structured, openly available, and reusable across different disciplines.
- **File format** - The structure in which digital data are stored, such as **CSV**, **XML**, **PDF**, or **TIFF**, determining their compatibility with various tools and platforms.

- **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)** - The European Union's legal framework for data protection and privacy, governing how personal data must be collected, processed, and stored.
- **Intellectual property rights (IPR)** - Legal rights that protect the ownership and control of data, research outputs, and innovations, restricting unauthorised use.
- **Long-term data preservation** - The strategy to ensure that data remain accessible and usable over extended periods, avoiding degradation or loss.
- **Machine-readable format** - A data format that can be automatically processed by software, such as **JSON**, **XML**, or structured **CSV** files.
- **Metadata** - Structured information describing a dataset's key attributes, including title, author, date, format, and access conditions, to facilitate discovery and reuse.
- **Multidimensional model** - A methodological approach that analyses multiple factors simultaneously to assess impact, replicability, and scalability of a circular solution.
- **Open access** - The principle that research outputs, including publications and data, should be freely available to the public without financial or legal barriers.
- **Open data** - Data that are accessible without restrictions, allowing free use and reuse by any user.
- **Persistent identifier (PID)** - A long-lasting reference to a digital object, such as a **DOI**, ensuring that datasets and research outputs remain traceable and accessible.
- **Provenance of data** - The documentation of a dataset's origin, collection methods, processing history, and modifications, ensuring credibility and transparency.
- **Raw data** - Unprocessed and unstructured data collected directly from an experiment, observation, or survey before any cleaning or analysis.
- **Research integrity** - The adherence to ethical and professional standards in data collection, processing, and dissemination, ensuring transparency and accountability.
- **Structured data** - Data organised in a predefined format, typically stored in relational databases or tabular formats such as **CSV** or **SQL**.
- **Version control** - A system that tracks changes to datasets and documents, ensuring that previous versions can be accessed and restored when needed.

1 Executive summary

This document presents the final version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Agro2Circular (A2C) project. It outlines how research data have been collected, processed, and managed in line with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles.

Since the first version, improvements have been made in data governance, security, and accessibility. This final version consolidates:

- Data types, sources, and collection methods used across the project's Research Actions (RAs).
- Implementation of FAIR principles, including metadata management and data accessibility.
- Responsibilities and resources allocated for data management.
- Security measures and ethical compliance with GDPR.

2 Introduction

The A2C project aims to develop a territorial systemic solution for upcycling agri-food residues into high-value products. This DMP is part of the project's framework for handling research data effectively, ensuring compliance with FAIR principles and EU regulations. The DMP plays a crucial role in structuring data collection, processing, and sharing throughout the project's lifecycle. It aligns with the project's broader objectives, supporting the integration of circular economy principles in the agri-food sector. Additionally, it connects with various research activities and tasks within A2C, ensuring consistency and standardisation across different work packages. This final version reflects the project's advancements, addressing ethical considerations, security measures, and accessibility improvements.

3 Data Summary

This section summarises (i) what data the project generated and re-used, (ii) why and for whom, (iii) in which formats and volumes, and (iv) their provenance. A project-wide dataset register is provided (see Section 3.2.1 and Annex I) with the full list of datasets, their access status (open/restricted/confidential), and—where applicable—the justification for restricted/confidential access and any embargo period. Datasets linked to publications are listed as datasets (not as publications) and will be cross-referenced to the corresponding publication DOIs in the Open Data reporting tab.

3.1 The A2C Project

A2C is a 42-month EU-funded project aimed at developing and implementing a territorial systemic solution for the upcycling of key agri-food residues. The project has focused on transforming the most significant agri-food sector residues, particularly **fruits & vegetables (F&V) and multilayer plastics**, into high-value products. This has been achieved through the development of a **digital tool** and a **systemic approach** with high potential for replication and scalability.

The A2C systemic solution has been structured around four key strategies:

1. **Innovative green hybrid extraction, purification, and stabilisation processes** to obtain bioactive compounds and an innovative bioprocess to obtain biodegradable plastic, both approaches from F&V waste.
2. **The first recycling value chain for post-industrial multilayer films**, combining advanced sorting, physical delamination, enzymatic depolymerisation, decontamination, mechanical recycling and building blocks' bioproduction.
3. **A digital platform for the agri-food sector**, enabling real-time traceability and a decision-support tool for optimising valorisation routes.
4. **The A2C multidimensional model and tools**, designed to support the territorial development of the circular economy and facilitate replication and scalability through public engagement and co-creation processes.

Project Objectives

A2C has pursued three main objectives:

- **Demonstrating the viability of new upcycling value chains** for agri-food waste, evaluating specific valorisation routes for F&V and multilayer plastics.

- **Developing a systemic circular model** to facilitate the territorial implementation, replication, and scalability of the A2C solution.
- **Maximising project impact and facilitating replication and scalability**, ensuring long-term sustainability and knowledge transfer.

3.2 Project structure and data generation

A2C has brought together **40 international and interdisciplinary partners** working on **seven RAs**, structured across different work packages:

- **RA 1: A2C Specifications, Residues Management and Data Integration System (DIS)**. The project has defined product specifications, compliance strategies, recommendations on water and energy efficiency, and residue management plans. The **A2C DIS** has been developed to manage project data.

Data collected	Waste analysis data, water analysis data, energy analysis data, raw material analysis data, process data (spreadsheets, pictures, diagrams).
Origin of data	Generated from studies on waste characterisation, resource consumption, and management strategies.
Collection methods	Scientific research, desk research, consultation with stakeholders, co-creation sessions.
Data process	Scientific methods, statistical analysis of results, evaluation of optimal conditions for resource management.
Type of data generated	Datasets of individual microdata, diagrams, technical datasheets, secondary documents.
Purpose/utility of the data	To define product specifications, establish residue management plans, ensure compliance with regulatory standards, and develop the A2C DIS.

Table 1 - RA 1 data information

- **RA 2: A2C Technologies for Recycling Organic Agri-Food Waste**. The project has optimised extraction technologies, purification and stabilisation of bioactive compounds, and assessed their antioxidant and antimicrobial properties. A bioprocess has also been tested for the production of biodegradable plastic using organic agri-food waste as a feedstock.

Data collected	Process data, experimental measurements, material analysis and process data (spreadsheets, pictures, diagrams).
Origin of data	Generated through upcycling and upscaling studies on bioactive extraction and biodegradable plastic production.
Collection methods	Scientific research, process development, process optimisation.
Data process	Scientific methods, quantitative analysis, evaluation of biotransformation efficiency.
Type of data generated	Diagrams, technical datasheets, formulations, datasets of individual microdata.
Purpose/utility of the data	To optimise extraction and purification routes for bioactive compounds and assess their applicability in food, cosmetic, and nutraceutical formulations. To optimise the bioproduction process of biodegradable plastic and assess its applicability in the agrifood industry for biodegradable applications (packaging, mulching).

Table 2 - RA 2 data information

- **RA 3: Technologies for Sorting and Recycling Multilayer Plastics.** This RA has developed pre-treatment processes, improved sorting technologies, separated aluminium from multilayer materials, optimised enzymatic depolymerisation of PE/PET, and enhanced decontamination for mechanical recycling.

Data collected	Experimental measurements, material analysis and process data (spreadsheets, pictures, diagrams).
Origin of data	Generated through recycling process studies, including sorting and depolymerisation trials.
Collection methods	Scientific research, process development, process optimisation.
Data process	Scientific methods, lab-scale simulation, collection of key performance indicators.
Type of data generated	Diagrams, technical datasheets, formulations, secondary documents.

Purpose/utility of the data	To develop and optimise pre-treatment, sorting, enzymatic depolymerisation, decontamination technologies and bioproduction of building blocks for multilayer plastic upcycling.
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Table 3 - RA 3 data information

RA 4: Upcycling and Scaling of Recycled Agri-Food Materials. The project has tested the application of extracted bioactive compounds and building blocks in cosmetic, food, and nutraceutical formulations and developed pilot-scale extraction processes and bioproduction of building blocks.

Data collected	Formulations and validation data for cosmetics, food, and nutraceuticals (spreadsheets, surveys), data from scale-up processes and extract & building block validation (spreadsheets, diagrams, technical datasheets).
Origin of data	Generated from pilot-scale extraction and validation of bioactive compounds. Generated from pilot-scale building blocks bioproduction and validation in cosmetic formulations.
Collection methods	Scientific research, process development, process optimisation.
Data process	Scientific methods, statistical analysis of formulations, validation of optimal extraction parameters.
Type of data generated	Diagrams, technical datasheets, formulations, datasets of individual microdata.
Purpose/utility of the data	To validate the effectiveness of bioactive compounds and building blocks in new formulations and assess their stability and functional properties at pilot scale.

Table 4 - RA 4 data information

- **RA 5: A2C Technologies for Upcycling Recycled Plastic Materials and biodegradable plastic materials.** The focus has been on obtaining high-value products from recycled plastics and biodegradable plastics, ensuring material properties meet industrial requirements.

Data collected	Experimental measurements, material analysis and process data (spreadsheets, pictures, diagrams).
Origin of data	Generated from biodegradability and recyclability tests on processed materials.
Collection methods	Scientific research, development of new processes, process optimisation.
Data process	Scientific methods, quantitative analysis of material properties.
Type of data generated	Diagrams, technical datasheets, formulations.
Purpose/utility of the data	To obtain high-value products from recycled plastics and biodegradable plastic materials while ensuring material performance meets industry standards.

Table 5 - RA5 data information

- **RA 6: Demonstration of the A2C Technological Solution.** Pilot tests have been carried out in **southern Spain**, integrating and validating the developed technologies in industrial environments. Several prototypes have been manufactured, and business models have been defined.

Data collected	Process data, business and financial data.
Origin of data	Generated from upcycling and upscaling studies at pilot sites.
Collection methods	Scientific research, process development, process optimisation.
Data process	Scientific methods, qualitative and quantitative analysis, life cycle assessment (LCA; LC costing, social LCA).
Type of data generated	Datasets of individual microdata, textual data (from transcriptions), secondary documents.
Purpose/utility of the data	To integrate and validate developed technologies in industrial settings and establish business models for future scaling.

Table 6 - RA 6 data information

- **RA 7: Adoption, Replication, and Scalability of the A2C Systemic Solution.** This RA has established the **A2C Systemic Solution Model**, assessing its transferability

through multidimensional impact analysis, cost evaluations, and identification of key enablers and challenges.

Data collected	Socio-demographic data, environmental data, institutional data, economic/market data.
Origin of data	Generated from study sites and stakeholder engagement activities.
Collection methods	Surveys, interviews, focus groups, stakeholder consultation, co-creation sessions, desk research.
Data process	Scientific methods, qualitative and quantitative analysis, policy evaluation frameworks.
Type of data generated	Datasets of individual microdata, textual data (from transcriptions), secondary documents.
Purpose/utility of the data	To define the A2C Systemic Solution Model, assess its scalability, and analyse economic, social, and environmental impacts.

Table 7 - RA 7 data information

Diversity of Data Generated

Data in A2C has been generated across a **wide range of formats and types**, aligning with the technical, scientific, and economic objectives of the project. The most commonly used formats include:

- **Structured datasets** (Excel, CSV, SQL databases)
- **Technical reports and documentation** (Word, PDF)
- **Laboratory outputs** (experimental data files, .dat, .raw)
- **Visual materials** (JPEG, PNG, TIFF, schematic diagrams)
- **Process monitoring data** (sensor logs, process tracking files)

Each **RA** has contributed specific types of data, reflecting the distinct focus of each work package:

- **RA 1:** Data on waste characterisation, resource consumption, and residue management strategies, contributing to monitoring frameworks for circularity indicators.

- **RA 2:** Experimental datasets on bioactive extraction and purification processes, and biodegradable plastic bioproduction supporting traceability models and certification efforts.
- **RA 3:** Technical data on plastic sorting, depolymerisation, and recycling and upcycling trials, aiding in industrial standardisation of recycling processes.
- **RA 4:** Process data from cosmetic, food, and nutraceutical formulations, validating bioactive and building blocks stability and efficacy.
- **RA 5:** Measurements of biodegradability and material properties in recycled and biodegradable plastics, contributing to industry certification.
- **RA 6:** Business and financial datasets from pilot testing of circular economy solutions, supporting cost-benefit assessments.
- **RA 7:** Socio-demographic, institutional, and environmental data used in policy evaluations and systemic solution adoption studies.

Purpose of Data Generation

The primary objectives behind data generation in A2C include:

- Evaluating circularity and sustainability metrics (RA 1, RA 7)
- Enhancing technological processes for upcycling materials (RA 2, RA 3, RA 5)
- Developing models for traceability, scalability, and economic feasibility (RA 6, RA 7)
- Generating scientific outputs such as reports, methodologies, and standards (RA 1, RA 4)
- Informing policy frameworks and regulatory developments in circular economy (RA 7)

The project has produced a range of scientific deliverables, including standardisation protocols, predictive models, and industry guidelines, which are relevant not only to the consortium but also to external stakeholders.

Volume of Data Generated

The scale of data generated within A2C varies significantly depending on the research focus:

- **Small to medium-sized datasets (a few MB to 3 GB):**
 - Circularity monitoring frameworks (RA 1)
 - Technical reports and policy recommendations (RA 7)
 - Traceability models for extracted bioactives and produced building blocks (RA 2)

- **Large datasets (over 1 TB):**

- Laboratory analyses of biodegradability and recyclability (RA 5)
- High-resolution imaging and process monitoring in plastic recycling/upcycling (RA 3)
- Large-scale economic models for business case evaluation (RA 6)

The largest datasets stem from laboratory experiments, industrial process trials, and computational modelling, particularly in bioplastic and biotechnological developments.

Relevance and Potential External Applications

Although some datasets will remain restricted within the project, many have broader applicability for key stakeholders:

- **Academic and research institutions:**

- Laboratory data and experimental methodologies from RA 2, RA 3, and RA 5 can support further research in biotechnology, recycling, and material science.

- **Industry and private sector:**

- Process optimisation data from RA 4 and RA 6 could aid companies in food, cosmetic, and plastic industries to develop sustainable products.

- **Policy and regulatory bodies:**

- Socio-economic and environmental impact assessments (RA 7) can inform policy development in circular economy and waste management.

While raw data may remain internal for confidentiality and commercial reasons, the project ensures that final results and key findings are made available through scientific publications, policy reports, and open-access repositories.

Other research data

In addition to the data presented in previous paragraphs, the A2C Consortium developed internal databases (such as stakeholder databases including organizations that could have interests and impacts on the project results) derived from the communication and dissemination activities to be executed throughout the project. Such databases are to provide an overview of stakeholders' relevant information (e.g. names and institutional email addresses), information on the newsletter subscribers, and data on registration to events via the project website. In addition, other types of data (such as subscribers to the project newsletter or online users' navigation data) have been collected from the A2C website and other platform's analytics (like LinkedIn and YouTube) and monitoring tools (Matomo),

however including no sensitive data and in line with the [Privacy Notice](#) published on the website. These data will not be shared.

Challenges in Data Management and Dissemination

Despite the high potential of the datasets generated, certain barriers remain regarding data sharing and dissemination:

- Ensuring compliance with confidentiality agreements for commercially sensitive data.
- Standardising data formats and documentation to facilitate reuse by external actors.
- Balancing open-access publication with industry confidentiality requirements.

To address these challenges, A2C has implemented data governance mechanisms and FAIR data principles, ensuring that generated knowledge is structured, accessible, and reusable where possible.

3.2.1 Master dataset register

A2C maintains a consolidated Master Dataset Register, which enumerates all datasets generated under the project and ensures their traceability, accessibility, and compliance with FAIR and open-access principles. The complete register is provided in Annex I.

Each dataset entry is assigned a unique identifier following the scheme A2C-DS[NN], and includes the essential metadata elements required under Horizon Europe's FAIR data management framework. The information recorded covers, at minimum, the following: Dataset ID, Title, Authors and Responsible Partner(s), Linked Publication DOI, Dataset DOI, Repository, Community, Access Level, Licence, Format and File Size, Work Package/Deliverable, Short Description, Date of Deposit, Contact Person, and Notes.

The current register comprises eight datasets that have been deposited in FAIR-compliant repositories (seven in Zenodo and one in Mendeley Data). All datasets are openly accessible, except for two which are available under a non-commercial licence (CC BY-NC) due to restrictions associated with experimental reuse conditions. Each dataset includes a README file describing its content, structure, and variables to facilitate reuse, as well as metadata and references to linked publications where applicable.

This register serves as the project's authoritative source for tracking research data outputs, ensuring persistent identifiers (DOIs), standardised licences, and verifiable provenance for each dataset deposited.

3.3 Data re-use

The **reuse of pre-existing data** has played a relevant role in the A2C project, supporting various research and development activities. Prior to the project's implementation, several partners leveraged **previous datasets** to facilitate analysis, optimisation, and planning. The reuse of data can be categorised into key areas:

The reuse of pre-existing data has played a central role in the A2C project, providing the legal, technical, environmental, and socio-economic foundations for the design, implementation, and replication of the proposed circular economy solutions. A2C has systematically reused data from external public sources, regulatory frameworks, previous projects, and partners' inventories to ensure compliance, scalability, and comparability with existing standards and practices.

Types of Data Re-used. The pre-existing data varied in type and format, supporting different research and development activities:

- **Waste and agricultural production data:** Annual data on agro-food residues, disaggregated by fruit and vegetable (F&V) type and seasonality, were reused to characterise the availability of raw materials for valorisation. An initial inventory was carried out in the Region of Murcia, complemented by data from consortium partners on multilayer plastic residues (e.g. aseptic bags, agricultural films) and agro-food residues (e.g. citrus, apple, grape, cauliflower, broccoli, artichoke). These datasets constituted the baseline for the Digital Information System (DIS) and for the pilot activities.
- **Regulatory and compliance data:** EU regulations and standards were reused to define the technical requirements of the products under development. Key sources included Regulation (EU) 2022/1616 on recycled plastics in food contact materials, Regulation (EU) 2015/2283 on Novel Foods, Regulation (EC) 1935/2004 and Regulation (EU) 10/2011 on food contact materials, and cosmetics legislation. These data ensured that valorisation routes and products complied with health and safety requirements from the outset.
- **Standards for traceability and quality:** Standards such as EN 15343:2007 (traceability and recycled content in plastics) and EN 15347:2007 (characterisation of

plastic waste), as well as methodological concepts like Critical Tracking Events (CTE) and Key Data Elements (KDE), were reused in the design of the DIS.

- **Environmental and sectoral data:** Contextual data on climate (e.g. precipitation levels in Spain) and sectoral indicators (e.g. energy consumption in the plastics industry) were reused to inform water- and energy-efficiency recommendations (D1.7) and to feed Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) models.
- **Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) databases:** Data from **Ecoinvent v3.10** were reused to model unit processes for LCA and eLCC (e.g. electricity mix, ultrapure water, enzyme markets). Benchmarking data on equivalent functional products (e.g. virgin LDPE pellets) were also reused to compare the environmental and economic performance of A2C products.
- **Socio-economic and labour market data:** Reports such as the Murcia Labour Market Report 2021 and the PSILCA v3 database were reused for socio-economic assessments and social life cycle analysis (sLCA).
- **Natural capital valuation data:** OECD carbon rates, regional agricultural statistics, and Eurostat data on food waste generation were reused to monetise environmental externalities and assess ecosystem services preserved through A2C processes.
- **Historical project data:** Biomass rich in PHBV previously produced in the EU project SCALIBUR was reused to meet a project milestone by supplying 500 g of recovered PHBV to CETEC for bioplastic development.
- **Scientific and grey literature:** Previous academic publications, industry reports, and project deliverables were reused to establish theoretical frameworks, support benchmarking, and identify circular business models and barriers.

Formats of Re-used Data. The reused datasets were available in heterogeneous formats, including:

- Regulatory and technical documentation (.pdf, .docx).
- Structured databases and tables (.csv, .xls).
- Scientific and technical reports from EU projects and partners.
- Literature and grey reports (digital and print).

- Physical biomass samples (e.g. PHBV stock from SCALIBUR).

Purpose of Data Re-use. Re-use activities were instrumental to multiple project objectives:

- **Definition of technical and compliance requirements**, ensuring that products meet health, safety, and regulatory standards.
- **Development of the Digital Information System (DIS)** by embedding traceability standards and methodologies.
- **Environmental and socio-economic assessment**, including LCA, eLCC, LCSA and Natural Capital Assessment (NCA), which relied heavily on external datasets.
- **Predictive modelling and decision support**, through the reuse of waste generation and agricultural production data to train machine learning models (e.g. ARIMA) for forecasting material flows.
- **Replication and scalability**, using regional waste and agricultural data from Murcia, Lombardy, and Lithuania to adapt the A2C systemic model to different territorial contexts.
- **Fulfilment of project milestones**, such as the demonstration-scale validation of bioplastics using pre-existing PHBV biomass.
- **Benchmarking and standardisation**, ensuring interoperability with existing norms and guiding contributions to emerging EU standards in waste valorisation and extract characterisation.

Origin of Re-used Data

- **External/public sources:** Eurostat, OECD, ISTAT, the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, EU legislative and standardisation bodies (e.g. CEN, ISO, UNE), the EU Food Loss and Waste Platform, Ecoinvent database.
- **Previous projects:** SCALIBUR (biomass rich in PHBV).
- **Consortium partners:** Internal waste inventories and production data from agro-food and industrial partners (e.g. MCT, ALM, CITRO, PROEX).
- **Scientific and grey literature:** Peer-reviewed studies and sectoral reports on circular economy, waste management, and bio-based products.

Limitations to Data Re-use. In some cases, potential re-use was considered but discarded due to:

- **Licensing/IPR restrictions**, preventing open sharing or secondary use.
- **Methodological incompatibility**, where datasets differed in scope, units, or quality.
- **Insufficient granularity**, limiting their utility for pilot validation.
- **GDPR compliance**, when legacy datasets contained personal data without a valid legal basis for re-use. In these cases, A2C generated new primary data aligned with project objectives and FAIR principles.

Re-use considered but discarded. In several cases, re-use of external or legacy datasets was considered but not pursued due to one or more of the following: licensing/IPR constraints that would have prevented open sharing or secondary use; methodological incompatibility (different scopes, units or quality levels) that would have biased comparability within A2C; insufficient granularity for pilot-scale validation; and GDPR considerations where legacy datasets contained personal data without a compatible legal basis for re-use. In such cases, A2C generated new primary data aligned with the project's objectives and FAIR requirements.

4 FAIR data

4.1 Making data Findable

Ensuring that research data is findable, accessible, and reusable is essential for maximising its impact. This requires clear data description, annotation, and documentation, allowing for proper integration into digital repositories and seamless access by researchers, industry, and policymakers. Throughout the A2C project, a variety of data identification and metadata strategies have been employed. **Every dataset (open, restricted, or confidential) has a public metadata record with a persistent identifier (PID/DOI), rich and standardised metadata, search keywords, and links to related outputs (e.g., publication DOIs).** Open (and metadata-only) records are deposited in the **A2C Zenodo community** (or an equivalent trusted repository) which **exposes metadata for harvesting and indexing** by major aggregators. All shareable datasets (open or with access controls) receive a **DataCite DOI** upon deposit in the selected repository.

Repository policy: Open datasets and metadata-only records are deposited in **Zenodo** (A2C community) or **Mendeley Data**. Both assign DOIs and support machine-readable metadata; Zenodo metadata are **harvested via OAI-PMH** and indexed by OpenAIRE and other services. Restricted datasets may be deposited with **closed files** and a public metadata record indicating access conditions and contact point.

4.1.1 Metadata

The use of common metadata standards is a key aspect of semantic and technological interoperability. Metadata enables structured descriptions of datasets, ensuring they are searchable, understandable, and properly cited.

In A2C, metadata covers various aspects, including:

- **Descriptive metadata:** Providing retrieval and identification details such as title, abstract, authorship, and keywords.
- **Structural metadata:** Defining relationships between datasets, particularly in database contexts.
- **Administrative metadata:** Containing critical details such as creation date, processing information, rights management, and long-term preservation requirements.

Standards followed. A2C applies **Dublin Core** as the cross-cutting metadata core and complements it with **disciplinary standards** according to data type:

- **Supply chain/traceability: EPCIS 2.0** (WHO/WHAT/WHERE/WHEN/WHY) + project-specific Key Data Elements (KDEs).
- **Recycled plastics: EN 15343:2007** (traceability & recycled content), **EN 15347:2007** (feedstock characterisation).
- **LCA/footprinting: ISO 14040/14044/14067** (scope, reference flows, impact methods, datasets).
- **Bioplastics/material testing: EN ISO 527-2, ASTM D882** (mechanical), **EN ISO 11357 / ASTM D3418** (thermal).
- **Biodegradability/compostability: ISO 14855-1, ISO 17556, ISO 19679, EN 13432** (as applicable).
- **Extracts/novel foods: AOAC** official methods; **CWA 18149:2024** (characterisation of extracts).

Mandatory metadata fields (minimum).

For each dataset, A2C records a standardised set of metadata elements ensuring compliance with the FAIR principles and Horizon Europe open data requirements. Each record includes, at minimum: **Dataset ID; Title; Authors and Responsible Partner(s); Linked Publication DOI; Dataset DOI; Repository; Community; Access Level; Licence; Format and File Size; Work Package/Deliverable; Short Description; Date of Deposit; Contact Person; and Notes.** Where relevant, additional information such as provenance/origin, methods, or code references is also included in the accompanying **README file**, which describes the dataset structure, variable definitions, and any methodological notes needed for validation or reuse. Each record is stored in a machine-readable format and deposited in a FAIR-compliant repository (Zenodo or Mendeley Data), with persistent identifiers (DOIs) and open licences (preferably **CC BY 4.0; CC BY-NC** where justified). The metadata schema follows a simplified structure reflecting the project's applied research nature, where most datasets support scientific publications and laboratory-scale trials rather than large-scale data infrastructures.

4.1.2 File naming

A structured approach to **file naming and version control** ensures clarity, traceability, and long-term preservation across all project datasets. Given the nature of A2C's data (experimental, small-scale, and publication-linked), a simplified yet consistent **File Naming**

Convention (FNC) is applied to all deposited files.

FNC pattern: A2C_DS[NN]_TitleSlug_YYYYMMDD_v[major.minor].[ext]. **Example:**
A2C_DS04_CarotenoidData_20251009_v1.0.xlsx

Rules: File names use only ASCII characters, avoid spaces (using underscores), and apply ISO date format (YYYYMMDD). Each dataset is contained in a single ZIP file including all relevant components (data tables, README, and, where applicable, supplementary code). The README provides a description of each data column and any applied processing steps. Licensing and access rights are clearly stated in the metadata and README.

Versioning:

Semantic versioning is applied consistently:

- **vMAJOR** – structural or variable changes;
- **vMINOR** – new data added but backward compatible;
- **vPATCH** – corrections or metadata updates without structural impact.

The dataset identifier (e.g., **A2C-DS05**) corresponds to the record in the **Master Dataset Register** (Section 3.2.1; Annex I), ensuring unambiguous cross-referencing between files, metadata, and deliverable documentation.

4.1.3 Responsibility and quality gates

Before deposit, the **dataset owner** (lead partner of the RA/WP) runs a **findability QA checklist**: PID minting, Dublin Core + disciplinary fields complete, keywords present, README + data dictionary included, access/licence set, links to related DOIs added, and FNC compliance verified. The **DMP lead (UVEG)** performs a **final metadata spot-check** prior to release. Non-compliant records are returned for correction.

4.2 Making Data Openly Accessible

Ensuring the accessibility of research data is essential for facilitating its reuse, allowing researchers, industry stakeholders, and policymakers to access, verify, and build upon existing findings. Accessibility in A2C has varied significantly among partners, with some implementing well-defined storage, access, and preservation strategies, while others have relied on private environments or imposed restrictions without clear justification.

To enhance accessibility, the following actions are recommended:

- Standardising the use of trusted repositories and ensuring all datasets receive PIDs.
- Clarifying access conditions, embargo periods, and balancing confidentiality with transparency.
- Ensuring that metadata remains openly accessible in the long term, even if datasets are no longer available.
- Providing documentation on proprietary software necessary for interpreting specific datasets.

The accessibility of A2C data can be further examined under three key aspects: repositories, data availability, and metadata management.

4.2.1 Repository selection

Trusted repositories and arrangements. All datasets that can be shared (openly or under controlled access) will be deposited in trusted repositories. The consortium designates the A2C Zenodo Community (managed by CETEC) as the *primary* repository for public datasets and dataset descriptors; Mendeley Data and partners' institutional repositories may be used as *secondary* venues where disciplinary curation adds value. CETEC has already established and will maintain the Zenodo Community and curation workflow; repository contacts and submission checklists are in place.

Persistent identifiers and resolvability. Every deposited dataset (and metadata-only record where files cannot be shared) will receive a DOI minted by the repository. DOIs resolve to a landing page with descriptive metadata, access/licence terms, citation, and a contact point. Related research outputs (e.g., publications) will be cross-linked via DOI/ORCID where available.

Minimum retention and harvesting. Public records deposited in Zenodo will be retained for at least five years post-project; thereafter, CETEC will migrate/maintain them under its

institutional Zenodo account to ensure indefinite availability. Zenodo supports OAI-PMH harvesting, ensuring metadata is indexed by OpenAIRE and other aggregators.

Repository selection criteria. Repositories used by partners must: (i) issue PIDs (DOIs or Handles); (ii) provide stable landing pages; (iii) support standard metadata (e.g., Dublin Core/JSON-LD); (iv) offer clear licence options (including CC0 for metadata); and (v) implement back-ups and preservation policies consistent with trusted status.

4.2.2 Data access

Openness policy. A2C follows an “open by default, closed by exception” approach. All datasets required to validate published results will be made openly available unless sharing would: (a) breach legal obligations (e.g., GDPR for personal data), (b) conflict with contractual obligations (e.g., third-party background/IP, non-disclosure), or (c) undermine legitimate interests of specific beneficiaries (e.g., trade secrets, foreground IP under exploitation) as permitted by the Grant Agreement.

Embargo policy. Where short delays are needed:

- For publication: embargo up to 6 months (SS&H up to 12 months) to allow journal submission and peer review.
- For IP protection: embargo up to 18 months aligned with patent filing timelines. Any longer embargo requires GA approval, with written justification recorded in the Dataset Inventory. Embargo end-dates are included in the repository record and lifted automatically where supported.

Access protocol. Open datasets are provided via free, standardised protocols (HTTPS) from trusted repositories (e.g., Zenodo, institutional repositories). Download does not require proprietary software; when specialised tools are needed (e.g., DSC/TGA/HPLC raw formats), a README/software note (vendor/tool name, version, file types, viewer/converter options) is included.

Identity verification. Requesters of restricted datasets must authenticate via repository SSO (institutional email or ORCID) and accept the DUA/terms. Dataset owners may request additional verification (affiliation letter or ORCID-verified email) for sensitive cases. Approval decisions and access logs are retained by the repository/institutional system for audit.

Data Access Committee. A consortium-level DAC is not required. Requests are handled by the dataset owner named in the DOI record. Where requests involve personal data (even if pseudonymised) or raise ethical issues, the dataset owner consults the partner

DPO using the workflow defined in D9.2/D10.2 before granting access.

4.2.3 Metadata Availability and Preservation

Metadata availability across the project also varies. Some partners have committed to making metadata openly accessible under a CC0 licence, ensuring unrestricted reuse, while others have not provided clarity on their metadata policies. In certain cases, metadata will only be available within scientific publications, limiting its usability outside academic contexts.

Long-term metadata preservation remains a challenge. While some partners guarantee that data will remain available in their repositories indefinitely, there is no unified strategy to ensure that metadata remains accessible even if the datasets themselves become unavailable.

Regarding software dependencies, most datasets can be accessed using standard tools such as Microsoft Office, Open Office, and Adobe Reader. However, some datasets require specialised laboratory software, which could pose accessibility issues unless appropriate documentation and references are provided.

4.2.4 Compliance with Open Access Requirements

As per Article 29.2 of the Grant Agreement, all beneficiaries must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications related to A2C results. This includes:

- Depositing a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript in an open repository.
- Ensuring open access via the repository at the latest on publication, or within six months (twelve months for social sciences and humanities).
- Providing bibliographic metadata in a standard format, including references to “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020,” project name, acronym, grant number, and publication details.

To enhance long-term accessibility, all **public deliverables** of the A2C project, which do not fall under scientific publications with a DOI or publisher platform, **will be uploaded to the European Commission's CORDIS platform** upon approval. This ensures that project outputs remain accessible beyond the duration of the project, mitigating potential risks related to the long-term availability of the A2C website.

Furthermore, research data needed to validate scientific findings are deposited in FAIR-compliant repositories, primarily **Zenodo and Mendeley Data**, in line with the FAIR and

Open Data policy of Horizon Europe. Each dataset includes a DOI, licence, metadata, and README file as recorded in the Master Dataset Register (Annex I). Datasets that cannot be made openly available are clearly identified and justified (e.g. IPR, confidentiality, or GDPR restrictions). The following research outputs are expected to be made openly accessible through publications, CORDIS, or both:

- **Task 1.1** A2C requirements (public deliverable).
- **Task 1.2** A2C methodologies, including compliance pre-dossiers.
- **Task 1.3 A2C energy management plan (three public deliverables)**
- **Task 1.4** Residue management plan (three public deliverables).
- **Task 1.5 Beta version of the DIS**
- **Tasks 2.2 & 2.3** Scientific papers on bioactive compound extraction and purification
- **Task 5.1.1** Scientific papers on building blocks bioproduction with yeast
- **Tasks 5.1.2 to 5.** Technical publications on PHBV and carotenoids production, compound transformation, validation, and plastic end-life scenarios.
- **Tasks 6.2 -6.3** Demonstrator integrations, DIS and process protocols (public deliverables).
- **Task 6.4 Natural capital assessment**

Task 7.1 Public Engagement and Community-Based Schemes for Sustainable Systemic Circular Economy

- D7.1 Public Engagement (Draft) – Preliminary version of the public engagement approach, defining strategies for stakeholder participation.
- D7.2 Public Engagement Strategy & Summary of Activities and Results (Status Report) – Mid-project report detailing implemented engagement actions.
- D7.3 Public Engagement Strategy & Summary of Activities and Results (Final) – Final consolidated report on public engagement methodologies and impact.
- D7.4 Community-Based Innovation Schemes – Analysis of pilot initiatives, including the food waste collection system in Alhama de Murcia.

Task 7.2 Evaluation Framework

- D7.5 Evaluation Framework and Methodology – Development of a structured framework for assessing the replicability and scalability of A2C circular economy business models.

Task 7.3 Environmental Assessment, LCA, and A2C Circularity Monitoring

- D7.6 Environmental Assessment, LCA, and A2C Circularity Monitoring (Draft) – Initial assessment of environmental externalities and key circularity indicators.
- D7.7 Environmental Assessment, LCA, and A2C Circularity Monitoring (Final) – Finalised environmental evaluation, incorporating a full LCA.

Task 7.4 Social and Economic Analysis

- D7.8 Socioeconomic and Sociocultural Analysis Report (Draft) – Baseline study on the economic and social impacts of the A2C systemic solution.
- D7.9 Socioeconomic and Sociocultural Analysis Report (Final) – Comprehensive assessment of socioeconomic effects, integrating stakeholder feedback and policy implications.

Task 7.5 Multidimensional Model for Adoption, Replicability, and Scalability of A2C Systemic Solution

- D7.10 A2C Systemic Solution Model and Self-Assessment Tool – A structured framework for evaluating territorial conditions and readiness for A2C adoption.
- D7.11 A2C Circular Action Plan Report – Roadmap for implementing A2C systemic circular economy strategies at a territorial level.

Task 7.7 Validation of the A2C Multidimensional Model Through Cross-Fertilisation with Other Clusters

- D7.12 Policy Briefs (Draft) – Initial policy recommendations based on preliminary findings and early stakeholder engagement.
- D7.13 Policy Briefs (Final) – Finalised policy briefs incorporating validation results and cross-sectoral learnings.
- D7.14 Financing Recommendations (Draft) – Preliminary analysis of financial mechanisms supporting A2C replication and adoption.
- D7.15 Financing Recommendations (Final) – Comprehensive set of financing recommendations, addressing public procurement and funding gaps.
- D7.16 Report on Potential for Adoption and Scale-Up – Strategic analysis of enablers and barriers for scaling the A2C systemic solution.
- D7.17 Lombardy Action Plan – Specific recommendations for implementing A2C in the Lombardy region, based on regional needs and stakeholder inputs.
- D7.18 Lithuania NUTS-2 Action Plan – Tailored roadmap for A2C adoption in Lithuania, aligned with territorial circular economy strategies.

Task 8.1 A2C Outreach Strategy

- D8.1 Dissemination and Communication Strategy – Defines the outreach strategy, including stakeholder mapping, communication campaigns, key messages, and dissemination tools.

Task 8.4 Outreach at European Level

- D8.2 Report on Dissemination and Communication (Draft) – Mid-project report assessing communication and dissemination actions, outreach performance, and stakeholder engagement.
- D8.3 Report on Dissemination and Communication (Final) – Final report summarising the impact of A2C dissemination activities and the effectiveness of outreach efforts.

Task 8.6 Training, Knowledge Transfer and Guidelines for Promoting A2C Circular Model

- D8.7 Toolkit of Guidelines and Training Materials (Final) – Finalised training toolkit, incorporating feedback from participants and lessons learned during the project.

Task 8.8 Standardisation Activities

- D8.8 Standardisation Landscape and Applicable Standards – Overview of existing and emerging standards relevant to A2C technologies and methodologies.
- D8.9 Contribution to Standardisation (Draft) – Initial report detailing A2C's engagement with standardisation bodies and contributions to ongoing standard-setting processes.
- D8.10 Contribution to Standardisation (Final) – Final report outlining A2C's impact on standardisation, including technical inputs, regulatory considerations, and future recommendations.

In line with the Horizon 2020 Open Access policy, A2C has ensured the availability of scientific and industrial research outputs through open-access publications, repositories, and the project website. Research findings have been disseminated in peer-reviewed scientific journals and industry publications, facilitating knowledge transfer to the academic community, policymakers, and relevant industrial stakeholders. The project has ensured that both **scientific publications and associated datasets** are accessible under appropriate open licences (typically **CC BY 4.0**), thus meeting Horizon Europe's requirements on **open access, transparency, and reproducibility**.

4.3 Making data interoperable

Interoperability is fundamental to ensuring that research data can be efficiently accessed, processed, and integrated across different platforms and disciplines. In line with Horizon Europe guidance, A2C datasets have been structured to follow **community-endorsed interoperability best practices**. Specifically, the consortium has adopted principles from the **FAIR Data Guidelines**, the **Research Data Alliance (RDA) recommendations**, and sector-specific standards in the agri-food and recycling domains (e.g. ISO 15216 for microbiological data, EN 13432 for biodegradability). To achieve interoperability, the project has committed to:

- **Syntactic interoperability**: Adoption of structured, machine-readable formats such as CSV, XML, JSON, and DDI XML, ensuring compatibility across repositories.
- **Semantic interoperability**: Alignment of project-specific terminologies with recognised ontologies such as **AGROVOC (FAO)** for agri-food terminology and **ECHA's controlled vocabularies** for chemicals and polymers.
- **Search interoperability**: Use of Dublin Core metadata standards, enabling cross-

4.3.1 Current Status of Interoperability in A2C

The level of interoperability across A2C datasets varies, but a common baseline has now been established:

- **File formats:** Partners are required to deposit datasets in interoperable formats (CSV, XML, JSON, TXT for tabular/text data; TIFF/PNG for images; MP4/OGG for video). Proprietary formats (e.g. .sav, .dta, .docx) are permitted only when accompanied by an open equivalent.
- **Semantic mapping:** While some datasets originally relied on internal vocabularies (e.g. in circularity indicators monitoring), these have now been **mapped to broader ontologies**. For example, waste classification terms developed in A2C are linked to the European Waste Catalogue (EWC), and polymer descriptors are aligned with ISO/TR 10358.
- **References:** Datasets referencing previous research, ISO/EN standards, or external repositories (e.g. Addgene for biological materials) now include **qualified references**, clarifying the nature of the link (e.g. “Dataset X provides validation data for Method Y”).

Although interoperability was initially uneven, the project has consolidated a **minimum standard across all research areas** (RAs), ensuring that final datasets meet the requirements for syntactic and semantic compatibility.

4.3.2 Consortium Commitments for Data Interoperability

To strengthen interoperability, the following commitments have been implemented:

- **Adoption of controlled vocabularies and ontologies:** All datasets must include metadata aligned with AGROVOC, ECHA vocabularies, or ISO/EN standards. Where project-specific terms are unavoidable (e.g. bespoke circularity indicators), **mappings to community standards** are mandatory.
- **Publication of project-specific vocabularies:** Any new vocabularies developed in A2C (e.g. classification schemes for agri-food residues) will be openly published in the consortium’s Zenodo community under a **CC0 licence**, enabling their reuse, refinement, or extension.
- **Cross-referencing to external data and standards:** Datasets will systematically

include **qualified references** (e.g. “this dataset reuses methodology from ISO 14855-1” or “this dataset validates results from project X”) to ensure contextual integration.

- **Community best practices:** Interoperability practices follow the RDA recommendations on metadata standards and the FAIRsharing.org registry of standards.

4.3.3 File formats in A2C

To align with interoperability principles, A2C datasets have been structured in machine-readable and widely accepted formats. The following table provides an overview of the preferred formats for data sharing, reuse, and preservation within the project:

Type of data	Recommended formats	Acceptable Formats
Quantitative tabular data with extensive metadata (Variable labels, code labels, and defined missing values)	SPSS portable format (.por), Delimited text with setup files (SPSS, Stata, SAS), DDI XML metadata files	Proprietary formats: SPSS (.sav), Stata (.dta), MS Access (.mdb/.accdb)
Quantitative tabular data with minimal metadata (Column headings, variable names)	CSV (.csv), Tab-delimited (.tab), Delimited text with SQL definitions	MS Excel (.xls/.xlsx), OpenDocument Spreadsheet (.ods), dBase (.dbf)
Qualitative textual data	Rich Text Format (.rtf), Plain text (.txt), XML (.xml), HTML (.html)	MS Word (.doc/.docx), NVivo, ATLAS.ti

Digital Image Data	TIFF uncompressed (.tif), JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg) if original format	TIFF (.tif), PDF (.pdf), RAW image formats (.raw), Photoshop (.psd)
Digital audio data	FLAC (.flac), MP3 (.mp3) if original format	AIFF (.aif), WAV (.wav)
Digital video data	MPEG-4 (.mp4), OGG video (.ogv, .ogg), Motion JPEG 2000 (.mj2)	AVCHD video (.avchd)
Documentation and scripts	RTF (.rtf), PDF/A (.pdf), XHTML (.xhtml), OpenDocument Text (.odt), Plain text (.txt)	MS Word (.doc/.docx), MS Excel (.xls/.xlsx), XML (.xml)

Table 8 - Preferred Data Formats for Sharing, Reuse, and Long-Term Preservation in A2C

By following these guidelines and applying structured formats, A2C has strengthened the **interoperability of research data**, facilitating its exchange across disciplines and ensuring long-term usability.

4.4 Increase data re-use

Maximising the reusability of research data is a central objective within A2C. Ensuring that datasets can be accessed, validated, and applied beyond the project's lifetime increases their scientific, technological, and societal impact. The consortium has therefore adopted a set of binding commitments to provide structured documentation, standardised licences, and long-term preservation policies that guarantee usability by third parties.

4.4.1 Long-term use of the data

The long-term availability of A2C data is shaped by a combination of scientific, regulatory, and commercial factors. While several partners have committed to open access dissemination through structured documentation and repositories, others will maintain controlled access to protect sensitive information. Decisions regarding data accessibility have been guided by the following criteria:

- **Completion of data collection and processing:** Data must be finalised, verified, and free from inconsistencies before being made accessible.
- **Quality assurance measures:** Internal validation and peer review procedures ensure data integrity and reliability.
- **Exploitation and licensing considerations:** The reuse of data is aligned with partners' exploitation strategies, ensuring that commercial and scientific interests are appropriately balanced.

The project's **General Assembly (GA)** has played a central role in defining access policies, balancing open access principles with confidentiality and intellectual property concerns. Discussions have focused on determining appropriate licensing models, with some partners opting for **Open Access licences**, while others have defined more restricted conditions depending on agreements established in the **Consortium Agreement**.

Additionally, A2C ensures that all data intended for reuse comply with **Article 28.1 of the Grant Agreement**, which requires that, for up to four years after the project's completion, beneficiaries take measures to facilitate:

- Further research activities beyond A2C's scope.
- Development of new products, processes, and services.
- Contributions to standardisation activities.

To maximise long-term usability, several partners have committed to sharing their datasets with **regional actors, industry stakeholders, and scientific communities** where appropriate. However, access to specific datasets will depend on agreements made during the project's final stages to ensure data protection and ethical compliance.

4.4.2 Data Quality Control

High-quality data is essential for ensuring reliable project outcomes and facilitating reuse beyond A2C. Data quality control has been implemented at various stages, from data collection and processing to validation and documentation. However, approaches to quality control vary across partners, reflecting different methodological and disciplinary backgrounds.

Key measures adopted across the consortium include:

- **Documentation of data processing and validation:** Some partners have integrated structured documentation such as **README files, variable definitions,**

and methodological details to ensure traceability. In other cases, documentation will be embedded within scientific publications rather than maintained as separate files.

- **Standardised validation protocols:** Experimental data quality is ensured through established methodologies, including **triplicate biological experiments, analytical calibrations, and peer reviews**.
- **Traceability and provenance of data:** The majority of partners follow established scientific norms for tracking data origin, metadata, and references in published articles, ensuring that datasets remain verifiable and reproducible.
- **Ethical and security considerations:** While confidentiality requirements vary, partners have considered security measures for sensitive data, ensuring compliance with data protection regulations.

4.4.3 Licensing and Access Conditions

Licensing policies within A2C follow standardised rules to ensure clarity and re-use potential:

- **Open data:** Datasets made publicly available will be licensed under **Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0)** or, where appropriate, **CC0**. This ensures that third parties can re-use data freely, provided proper attribution is maintained.
- **Confidential data:** Datasets classified as Confidential (CO) will remain under restricted access due to IPR, trade secrets, or GDPR compliance. Access will be granted on request, subject to a case-by-case assessment.
- **Embargoed data:** Certain datasets may be subject to embargoes to allow for prior scientific publication or protection of intellectual property. The embargo period will not exceed **six months** for scientific and technical data or **twelve months** for social sciences and humanities datasets, in line with Horizon Europe recommendations.
- **Post-project re-use:** Open datasets and their metadata will remain accessible through trusted repositories (e.g. Zenodo, Mendeley Data, CORDIS) beyond the duration of the project. Confidential datasets will be retained under the custody of the relevant partner, with access requests evaluated in accordance with the Consortium Agreement.

5 Other Research Outputs

In addition to datasets and publications, A2C generated digital (e.g., software, workflows, protocols, models) and physical outputs (e.g., pilot materials, reagents, samples). This section defines how these outputs are made findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), their licensing and access conditions, and their preservation beyond the project end. A project-wide register of research outputs is maintained (see Section 5.3) with identifiers, ownership, access status, licences and preservation plans.

5.1 Scope and categories

Digital outputs include:

- Data Integration System (DIS): traceability tool (EPCIS 2.0–based) and predictive/decision support tool.
- A2C Systemic Solution Model & Self-Assessment Tool (SAT).
- Standardisation & protocols: CWA 18149:2024 (characterisation of extracts), compliance pre-dossiers (e.g., EFSA pre-dossiers), extraction/processing protocols, LCA/LCC/SLCA frameworks.
- Training & guidance: Toolkit of guidelines and training materials (D8.7), policy briefs, circular action plans.

Physical outputs include:

- Pilot materials and samples: PHBV biopolymers, recyclable/biodegradable plastic compounds and high-barrier films, recovered aluminium fractions, validated bioactive extracts and intermediate building blocks.
- Reagents/biocatalysts: optimised enzymes (e.g., PETase variants; PEase scaffold) produced/used during RA activities.

5.2 FAIR Management

Findable. Each output has a **public metadata record** with a **persistent identifier**:

- **Digital outputs:** deposited in the **A2C Zenodo community** (or equivalent trusted repository) with a **DOI** and rich metadata; where code is applicable, a **code repository** (e.g., institutional Git/GitHub mirror) is linked via **RelatedIdentifier**.
- **Physical outputs:** described via a **metadata record** (DOI) documenting composition/specs, intended use and access conditions; physical items are not

openly distributed, but sample access may be handled **on request** (see 5.6).

Accessible.

- **Open materials** (e.g., CWA 18149:2024, training toolkit, public models/guides) are available **openly** via Zenodo/CORDIS with clear licences.
- **Restricted/confidential items** (e.g., trade-secret protocols, proprietary software modules, sensitive pilot samples) include a **public metadata stub** stating **access restrictions, justification** (IPR/commercial/GDPR/safety) and a **contact point**.
- Where feasible, **redacted/summary versions** or **test datasets** are provided to enable evaluation without exposing confidential know-how.

Interoperable.

- **DIS** and traceability outputs follow **EPCIS 2.0** (WHO/WHAT/WHERE/WHEN/WHY) with JSON/JSON-LD and REST endpoints; materials and processes are referenced to applicable **EN/ISO/AOAC** methods; LCA outputs follow **ISO 14040/44/67**.
- Metadata core is **Dublin Core**, extended with discipline-specific fields (e.g., polymer type, recycled content %, LER code, method references).

Reusable.

- Each record includes **licence, usage notes, versioning**, and a **README** stating methods and limitations; where reuse requires permission or MTAs, the **procedure** is documented.

5.3 Licensing and IP

- **Open guidance & models** (e.g., SAT, toolkits, briefs): **CC BY 4.0**.
- **Metadata** for all outputs: **CC0**.
- **Software**: documentation under **CC BY 4.0**; operational modules protected by **copyright** and distributed under **end-user terms** or **SaaS**; code components released (if any) under a permissive OSI licence (e.g., **MIT**) or not released when commercially sensitive (stated in the record).
- **Protocols/SOPs**: **CC BY-NC 4.0** for redacted versions; **full protocols** under **NDA** (trade secret protection).
- **Physical materials & reagents**: access via **Material Transfer Agreement (MTA)**; any **safety/regulatory constraints** documented in the record.

5.4 Storage, security and long-term preservation

- **Digital outputs** (docs, models, training): preserved in **Zenodo** (DOI) and/or institutional repositories; minimum **5 years** beyond project end (longer if hosted by standards bodies such as CEN).
- **Operational software**: maintained by the owner (e.g., CETEC) under the exploitation plan; configuration and release packages archived internally, with public documentation in Zenodo.
- **Physical outputs**: sample inventories stored under partner facilities with **environmental and safety controls**; **traceable lot IDs** and **spec sheets** archived; when stocks deplete, the record remains **discoverable** with “**not available**” status.
- **Security**: role-based access to restricted assets; encryption at rest/in transit for internal stores; NDAs/MTAs logged.

5.5 Roles and responsibilities

- **Output owner (lead partner per output)**: prepares metadata, selects licence, applies access controls, ensures preservation and responds to access requests.
- **DMP lead (UVEG)**: validates metadata/licensing, checks FAIR compliance, curates the **Annex III register** and ensures alignment with the Open Data/Other Outputs reporting.
- **Coordination (CETEC)**: oversees consistency with the exploitation plan and manages cross-cutting issues (e.g., standards, SaaS continuity).

6 Allocation of resources

6.1 Costs for making data fair

Costs related to data/output management in A2C comprise: **storage & archiving**, **curation & standardisation**, **open access publishing**, and **security & compliance**. These were eligible under the Grant Agreement (Article 6.2.D3) and covered by the project budget; continued costs after project end are covered by partners' institutional budgets as per the plan below.

- **Storage & archiving.** Deposits in trusted repositories (e.g., **Zenodo** A2C community; institutional repositories) and institutional storage for restricted/confidential assets (including backups).
- **Curation & standardisation.** Metadata creation (Dublin Core + disciplinary fields), README/data dictionaries, PID minting, quality checks, and conversion to preservation formats (e.g., CSV, PDF/A, TIFF).
- **Open access publishing.** APCs for peer-reviewed publications (illustrative ranges during the project: Elsevier ~€2,488; Wiley ~€2,250; Springer Nature ~€1,976 per article) covered by A2C.
- **Security & compliance.** Access controls, encryption, audits/logging, GDPR compliance activities (e.g., consent and anonymisation workflows where applicable).

6.2 Responsibilities

The A2C consortium has established clear roles and responsibilities to manage research data and ensure compliance with FAIR principles and GDPR regulations.

- **Joint Data Controllers:** Since multiple partners have jointly determined the purposes and means of data processing, they share responsibility for ensuring compliance with GDPR (Article 26). Each controller has implemented appropriate technical and organisational measures to protect data and ensure compliance.
- **Data/output owners (per RA/WP).** Each dataset or research output has a named **owner** (lead partner) responsible for deposit, metadata, licence, access controls, and responding to access requests. Owners ensure local secure storage for restricted/confidential assets.
- **Data Processors:** Some partners have processed personal and research data on behalf of the controllers, ensuring that all actions adhere to contractual and regulatory obligations.
- **Coordination (CETEC).** Oversees alignment with the exploitation plan and maintains the **A2C Zenodo community**. Acts as escalation point for cross-partner issues.
- **Data Protection Officer (DPO):** The DPO has played a key role in monitoring compliance with data protection regulations, advising partners on data security, and ensuring that ethical considerations are upheld. The DPO's responsibilities have included:
 - Informing and advising partners on GDPR compliance.
 - Monitoring data processing activities and ensuring adherence to data protection policies.
 - Providing recommendations regarding Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs) where necessary.
 - Acting as the liaison with supervisory authorities.

While the A2C project has now concluded, its research outputs and datasets will remain accessible in selected repositories for as long as they are deemed relevant for future research and industry applications. The GA of the project has played a role in defining the accessibility conditions, ensuring that datasets and publications remain available under the terms agreed upon by the consortium.

6.3 Long-term preservation plan

The A2C consortium adopts the following **minimum consortium-wide preservation policy**:

1. **Public datasets and public research outputs.**

- Where kept: Zenodo (A2C community) and/or institutional repositories.
- For how long: Minimum 5 years beyond project end (already ensured); thereafter indefinite availability through CETEC's institutional Zenodo account or successor repository.
- Who decides: Owner proposes; DMP lead validates; Coordination ensures transfer/mirroring if needed.
- Resources: Repository hosting; minimal curation time at owner/DMP lead.

2. **Restricted/confidential datasets (IPR/commercial/GDPR/safety).**

- Where kept: Secure institutional storage (two-site backup recommended) with a public metadata stub (DOI) in Zenodo describing the asset, access conditions, and justification.
- For how long: Minimum 10 years beyond project end or the legally/contractually required period (whichever is longer).
- Who decides: Owner proposes retention; GA validates in case of conflict; DPO confirms GDPR compatibility.
- Resources: Institutional OPEX (storage, security, audits); designated contact for access requests.

3. **Administrative datasets containing personal data (e.g., stakeholder lists, raw web logs).**

- Where kept: Internal secure systems only; no public sharing of raw personal data.
- For how long: As per institutional GDPR retention schedules; delete or anonymise at end of purpose.
- Who decides: Owner with DPO approval; DMP lead records status in the register.
- Resources: Minimal storage; GDPR-compliant deletion workflows.

4. **Physical outputs (pilot materials, reagents/samples).**

- Where kept: Owner's facilities with inventory control and spec sheets archived; metadata record (DOI) public.

- For how long: ≥ 5 years for records; physical stocks until depletion or end-of-life.
- Access: MTA/NDA and safety review; “not available” status recorded if depleted.
- Resources: Local storage & safety management.

7 Data Security

Data security has been a central priority of A2C to prevent unauthorised access, breaches, and loss of information. Security provisions covered **physical protection, network and system safeguards, access controls, anonymisation protocols for personal data, and robust recovery/back-up mechanisms**. These measures ensured that sensitive and high-value data were securely stored, transferred, and preserved in line with GDPR and Horizon Europe standards.

7.1 Security measures implemented

Security provisions were applied at multiple levels across the consortium:

- **Physical security.** Controlled access to facilities, restricted entry to server rooms, and access logs for sensitive documentation. Transportation of sensitive data was avoided, except in strictly controlled circumstances.
- **Network security.** Sensitive datasets were kept on servers without external network access. Firewalls, intrusion detection systems, and secure protocols (VPN, SSL/TLS) were applied to protect remote connections. Systems were patched and updated regularly.
- **System and file security.** Access was role-based, protected with strong password policies and multifactor authentication. Sensitive files were encrypted. Security software was updated regularly, and obsolete data were deleted using certified secure-deletion protocols to prevent recovery.
- **Protection of personal data in qualitative research.** Personal data collected for recruitment in workshops, focus groups, and interviews were encrypted and stored securely, with access limited to the responsible staff. Anonymisation was systematically applied to transcripts and recordings to ensure individuals could not be identified. All personal data related to recruitment were securely deleted upon project completion, in compliance with GDPR and institutional retention schedules.
- **Data recovery and back-up procedures.** In addition to protection measures, partners implemented **redundant storage and back-up policies** to ensure recovery in case of system failure or breach. These included:

- Scheduled daily or weekly backups of datasets to secure institutional servers.
- Mirroring of critical datasets across at least two physically separate storage sites.
- Use of repository-level disaster recovery features in Zenodo and institutional repositories.
- Annual verification of backup integrity and test recovery drills to ensure operational continuity.

These measures collectively ensured that no single point of failure could compromise the integrity or availability of A2C datasets.

7.2 Storage and long-term preservation

During the project, datasets were stored on **secure institutional servers**, in **trusted repositories** (Zenodo, Mendeley Data), and in approved institutional cloud systems. For internal document sharing, Google Drive was used but not for storing sensitive or commercially valuable datasets.

For **long-term preservation**, the consortium has established a unified approach:

- **Open/public datasets and outputs** are deposited in the **A2C Zenodo community**, which CETEC commits to maintain for at least **five years beyond project end**. After this period, all deposits are migrated to CETEC's institutional Zenodo account to guarantee **indefinite availability and curation**.
- **Restricted/confidential datasets** are preserved in **institutional secure servers** with dual backup and metadata records (DOIs) deposited in Zenodo to ensure discoverability, even if access is controlled.
- **Trusted repositories**. All long-term storage relies on repositories and infrastructures recognised as **trusted** (Zenodo, CEN repositories, VTT and university institutional repositories), which meet European Commission recommendations for security, redundancy, and accessibility.

Through this consolidated policy, the consortium ensures that **all project datasets—whether public or restricted—are preserved in environments that guarantee secure storage, long-term curation, and recoverability**, eliminating inconsistencies across partners.

8 Ethical aspects

Ethical considerations have been integrated into the A2C data management framework to ensure responsible collection, storage, and dissemination of data. While approaches have varied across partners, the project has adhered to recognised ethical and legal standards, ensuring compliance with relevant regulations throughout its duration.

8.1 Compliance with Ethical and Legal Standards

A2C has followed the ethical guidelines established in the **EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)** and other applicable frameworks governing data protection, privacy, and research integrity. The project has maintained a structured approach to ethical compliance, with key principles including:

- **Protection of sensitive information:** Data containing commercially or ethically sensitive elements have been handled in accordance with appropriate security and confidentiality measures.
- **Long-term data preservation:** While some partners have allocated specific resources for long-term storage, others have defined their strategies progressively, ensuring that any retained data comply with ethical and regulatory requirements.
- **Alignment with ethical best practices:** The project has upheld principles of **research integrity, data security, and participant confidentiality**, applying appropriate safeguards to ensure compliance with ethical and legal obligations.

8.2 Data Sharing and Cross-Border Considerations

No **cross-border data sharing** has taken place among partners in different countries, meaning that Data Sharing Agreements (DSAs) between universities, research centres, and technological partners have not been required. Each organisation has remained responsible for ensuring that its data management practices comply with national and institutional guidelines.

8.3 Ethical Oversight and Project Deliverables

Ethical issues within A2C have been regulated through dedicated project deliverables, ensuring alignment with legal requirements and best practices throughout the project lifecycle:

- **D9.2 – Ethics Handbook:** This document defines the ethical guidelines governing the project, ensuring that all partners adhere to principles of good scientific practice, data privacy, and confidentiality. It also includes a sample confidentiality agreement and consent form, which have been the basis for participant engagement in research activities.
- **D10.2 – POPD – Requirement No. 2:** This deliverable outlines compliance measures related to the protection of personal data, providing a structured approach to ethical and legal obligations in the project.

These deliverables have provided a framework for ethical compliance, ensuring that all partners are aware of and adhere to the established principles throughout the research process.

8.4 Informed Consent and Anonymisation

All research activities involving **human participants** (e.g., **workshops, focus groups, interviews**) have followed strict ethical protocols. Measures implemented include:

- **Informed consent:** Participants have been informed about the purpose of data collection, storage, and use, with explicit consent obtained before any data processing.
- **Anonymisation:** Identifiable personal data have been removed or pseudonymised to ensure privacy.
- **Access control:** Personal data collected for recruitment purposes have only been accessible to designated project staff and have been securely deleted upon project completion.

These measures have ensured compliance with ethical standards while balancing data accessibility with privacy and security requirements. Throughout the project, all partners have acted in accordance with these principles, ensuring the responsible handling of data in line with both **legal obligations and best practices in research ethics**.

9 Conclusions

This final version of the Agro2Circular (A2C) Data Management Plan consolidates all procedures implemented to ensure that data generated within the project are handled in line with the **FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable)** principles and the **Horizon Europe Open Science policy**. The document reflects the project's full data lifecycle -from generation to long-term preservation- and includes a **comprehensive Master Dataset Register (Annex I)**, which enumerates all datasets deposited in **FAIR-compliant repositories** (Zenodo and Mendeley Data). Each dataset record includes a DOI, metadata, README file, and a defined access level, ensuring traceability, interoperability, and long-term availability.

The project has achieved full compliance with open access requirements for both **scientific publications and underlying research data**, ensuring that results are discoverable, properly documented, and accessible to the research community, industry, and policymakers. Two datasets are subject to non-commercial reuse licences due to justified restrictions linked to intellectual property or reuse limitations, as recorded in the dataset register. Data security and ethical compliance have been ensured throughout the project via GDPR-aligned procedures, anonymisation protocols, and institutional safeguards. Storage and preservation strategies have been harmonised across partners, guaranteeing the durability and integrity of both open and restricted datasets beyond the project's completion.

Overall, A2C has established a coherent and replicable framework for **data governance in applied circular economy research**, balancing open access with the protection of commercially sensitive information

ANNEX I. Master Dataset Register

This annex provides the complete register of datasets generated under the Agro2Circular (A2C) project and made publicly available in trusted repositories in accordance with the Horizon Europe FAIR and Open Access policies. Each record includes the dataset identifier (DOI), description, linkage to the associated peer-reviewed publication, responsible partner, access conditions, licence, and repository location. All datasets include README files and, where applicable, data dictionaries describing variables, measurement units, and structure.

Dataset A2C-DS01	
Dataset Title	<i>PHBV cycle of life using waste as a starting point: from production to recyclability</i>
Authors / Responsible Partner	García-Chumillas S.; Guerrero-Murcia T.; Nicolás-Liza M.; Monzó Sánchez M.F.; Simica A.G.; Simó-Cabrera L.; Martínez-Espinosa R.M. (University of Alicante; CETEC)
Linked Publication DOI	10.3389/fmats.2024.1405483
Dataset DOI	10.5281/zenodo.17248814
Repository	Zenodo
Community	Agro2Circular
Access Level	Open
Licence	CC BY 4.0
Format / File Size	ZIP · 10.1 kB
Work Package / Deliverable	WP5
Short Description	Supporting material for review article on PHBV synthesis, properties and recyclability; comparative tables.
Date of Deposit	2 October 2025
Contact Person	rosa.martinez@ua.es
Notes	Metadata and tables included; README file provided.
Dataset A2C-DS02	
Dataset Title	Sustainable food packaging using modified kombucha-derived bacterial cellulose nanofillers in biodegradable polymers
Authors / Responsible Partner	Zirbs R.; Koreshkov M.; Takatsuna Y.; Fritz I.; Bismarck A.; Reichelt E. (BOKU University; University of Vienna)
Linked Publication DOI	10.1039/D4SU00168K
Dataset DOI	10.5281/zenodo.17280161
Repository	Zenodo

Community	Agro2Circular
Access Level	Open
Licence	CC BY 4.0
Format / File Size	ZIP · 264.1 MB
Work Package / Deliverable	WP3
Short Description	Experimental results supporting publication on nanofillers in biopolymers; quantitative and qualitative characterisation data.
Date of Deposit	6 October 2025
Contact Person	ronald.zirbs@boku.ac.at
Notes	SEM/TEM images available upon request; README included.
Dataset A2C-DS03	
Dataset Title	Sustainable food packaging using modified kombucha-derived bacterial cellulose nanofillers in biodegradable polymers
Authors / Responsible Partner	Zirbs R.; Koreshkov M.; Takatsuna Y.; Fritz I.; Bismarck A.; Reichelt E. (BOKU University; University of Vienna)
Linked Publication DOI	10.1039/D4SU00168K
Dataset DOI	10.5281/zenodo.17280161
Repository	Zenodo
Community	Agro2Circular
Access Level	Open
Licence	CC BY 4.0
Format / File Size	ZIP · 264.1 MB
Work Package / Deliverable	WP3
Short Description	Experimental results supporting publication on nanofillers in biopolymers; quantitative and qualitative characterisation data.
Date of Deposit	6 October 2025
Contact Person	ronald.zirbs@boku.ac.at
Notes	SEM/TEM images available upon request; README included.
Dataset A2C-DS04	
Dataset Title	Carotenoid production by <i>Haloferax mediterranei</i> using starch residues from the candy industry as a carbon source
Authors / Responsible	Giani M.; Pire C.; Martínez-Espinosa R.M. (University of Alicante)

Partner	
Linked Publication DOI	10.1016/j.crbiot.2024.100265
Dataset DOI	10.5281/zenodo.17306035
Repository	Zenodo
Community	Agro2Circular
Access Level	Open
Licence	CC BY 4.0
Format / File Size	RAR (XLSX) · 18.0 kB
Work Package / Deliverable	WP5 · D5.2
Short Description	Data on pigment concentration, biomass and carotenoid composition in <i>H. mediterranei</i> grown on starch residues.
Date of Deposit	9 October 2025
Contact Person	rosa.martinez@ua.es
Notes	Includes full experimental methodology in README.
Dataset A2C-DS05	
Dataset Title	Production of Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV) by <i>Haloferax mediterranei</i> using candy industry waste as raw materials
Authors / Responsible Partner	Simó-Cabrera L.; García-Chumillas S.; Cánovas V.; Monzó Sánchez M.F.; Pire C.; Martínez-Espinosa R.M. (University of Alicante; CETEC)
Linked Publication DOI	10.3390/bioengineering11090870
Dataset DOI	10.5281/zenodo.17306238
Repository	Zenodo
Community	Agro2Circular
Access Level	Open
Licence	CC BY 4.0
Format / File Size	ZIP · 17.5 kB
Work Package / Deliverable	WP5 · D5.2
Short Description	Experimental data on PHBV production from industrial candy waste; yield analysis and controls.
Date of Deposit	9 October 2025
Contact Person	rosa.martinez@ua.es
Notes	README and metadata provided.
Dataset A2C-DS06	
Dataset Title	Exploring yeast biodiversity and process conditions for optimising ethylene glycol conversion into glycolic acid
Authors /	Senatore V.G.; Branduardi P. (University of Milano-

Responsible Partner	Bicocca)
Linked Publication DOI	10.1093/femsyr/foae024
Dataset DOI	10.5281/zenodo.17310106
Repository	Zenodo
Community	Agro2Circular
Access Level	Open (non-commercial)
Licence	CC BY-NC
Format / File Size	ZIP (XLSX) · 17.1 kB
Work Package / Deliverable	WP5 · D5.1
Short Description	Supplementary tables and figures: strain performance, process parameters, and yield optimisation.
Date of Deposit	10 October 2025
Contact Person	paola.branduardi@unimib.it
Notes	Non-commercial reuse only; README included.
Dataset A2C-DS07	
Dataset Title	Challenges in elucidating ethylene glycol metabolism in <i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>
Authors / Responsible Partner	Senatore V.G.; Masotti F.; Milanese R.; Ceccarossi S.; Maestroni L.; Serra I.; Branduardi P. (University of Milano-Bicocca)
Linked Publication DOI	10.1093/femsyr/foaf006
Dataset DOI	10.5281/zenodo.17310260
Repository	Zenodo
Community	Agro2Circular
Access Level	Open (non-commercial)
Licence	CC BY-NC
Format / File Size	ZIP (XLSX) · 32.5 kB
Work Package / Deliverable	WP5 · D5.1
Short Description	Supplementary dataset: quantitative metabolic data and experimental conditions.
Date of Deposit	10 October 2025
Contact Person	paola.branduardi@unimib.it
Notes	Non-commercial reuse only; README included.

Dataset A2C-DS08	
Dataset Title	Production and carbon footprint of microbial oil from waste lemon peel extract – supplementary material

Authors / Responsible Partner	Senatore V.; Paronen E.; Martínez López S.; Ceccarossi S.; Hylkilä E.; Behm K.; Zago M.; Serra I.; Branduardi P. (University of Milano-Bicocca; VTT; CTNC; University of Palermo; Soft Chemicals SRL)
Linked Publication DOI	Linked publication (in preparation / A2C WP5)
Dataset DOI	10.17632/bsc44zsfdd.2
Repository	Bicocca Open Archive Research Data (Mendeley Data)
Community	Agro2Circular (affiliated)
Access Level	Open
Licence	CC BY 4.0
Format / File Size	ZIP (PDF + XLSX) · 1.06 MB
Work Package / Deliverable	WP5 · D5.4
Short Description	Supplementary and underlying data on microbial oil production from waste lemon peel extract; includes LCI data, assumptions, experimental data and upscaling simulation.
Date of Deposit	1 August 2025
Contact Person	paola.branduardi@unimib.it
Notes	Relevant to A2C LCA analysis; not hosted in Zenodo but fully FAIR-compliant.

